

Thermally Stable and Acidic Iron Oxide Pillared Clay

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Iron oxide pillared clay was prepared by interaction of bentonite with partially hydrolysed ferric chloride solution. The product was characterised by XRD and surface area (SA) measurement. Basal spacing and SA of the product, after calcination at 300°, were found to be 14.7 Å and 204 m² g⁻¹ respectively. It retained high SA (140 m² g⁻¹) even after heating at 500° for 2 h. Stepwise pyridine desorption study indicated that the clay retained high percentage (5%) of pyridine even after heating to 400°.

Naturally occurring clays had been used after acid modification for the cracking of oil¹. The synthesis of molecular sieve (zeolites) having high surface area, uniform pore size, high thermal and hydrothermal stability as well as high catalytic activity have replaced the clay as catalyst and catalyst support. However, the inherent problem of zeolites in processing heavy crude oil is their relatively small pore dimension (8.0 Å). In search for material having stable structure with large pores, basic concept of pillared clay has emerged and a new class of two-dimensional molecular sieve type materials have been prepared by intercalation of robust polyhydroxy metal cation into layered silicates (smectites) in late seventies²⁻⁴. The majority of work has tended to concentrate on the interaction of alumina or zirconia pillared clays since the solution chemistry of these metals is well studied and conditions for the formation of polyatomic hydroxy compounds of cationic type are well documented. Hydrolysis behaviour of Fe^{III} is similar to that of Al^{III} in forming polymeric cations. The hydroxy Fe^{III} cation is a promising pillaring agent. In spite of the few references⁵⁻¹³ for the iron oxide pillared clay as compared to alumina and zirconia pillared clays, high resistivity against hydrogen reduction and its usefulness as catalyst for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis has been observed by Kiyozumi *et al.*⁷. The selectivity for lower olefins is particularly noteworthy.

Burch and Warburton⁸ showed that iron oxide pillars could be converted into catalytically active sulphide pillars by mild sulphiding treatment. These materials were found to have better activity for the removal of Ni and V from crude oil than the original clay or alumina pillared clay. Besides its demetallisation property, highly dispersed Fe₂O₃ particles in iron-pillared clays have significant activity for hydrocracking⁹.

Thermal stability of the Fe^{II}-1,10-phenanthroline and Fe^{II}-tris-bipyridyl pillared clay^{10,11} is limited to 250–350°. The thermal decomposition of this complex¹² gave interlayer spacing of 8.4 Å with surface area of 20–60 m² g⁻¹ at 500°. Iron oxide pillars have been prepared successfully with

trinuclear acetate iron(III) ion as a pillaring agent. Since these complex ions are easily hydrolysed in water, use of fresh solution, low reaction temperature and immediate drying of the samples¹³ are essential. In the present study the interaction of partially hydrolysed Fe^{III} solution with H-form of clay has been made and surface area, basal spacing and pyridine retention data are presented.

Results and Discussion

Basal spacings of the iron-pillared clays prepared by the interaction of partially hydrolysed solution with OH/Fe ratio of 2.0 are shown in Fig. 1. The amount of Fe^{III} used for pillaring was 5.61 mM Fe/g of clay.

Results of XRD indicates a significant increase in basal spacing of iron-PILC (14.74 Å) compared to that of raw (ca. 9.7 Å). The cationic species which have large basal spacing on ion-exchange with interlayer cations of clay are considered to be hydrolysed products¹⁴ such as Fe(OH)²⁺, Fe(OH)₂⁺, Fe₂(OH)₄²⁺ and Fe₃(OH)₄⁺ which propagate by deprotonation of coordinated water molecules to discrete polycations of substantial size. Unlike a well defined [Al₁₃O₄(OH)₂₄(H₂O)₁₂]⁷⁺ cationic species¹, the size of polynuclear cationic iron species is difficult to control by hydrolysis of Fe^{III} solution with alkali. Instead of hydrolysing the Fe^{III} solution, in the present investigation, the freshly prepared Fe(OH)₃ was depolymerised by adjusting OH/Fe ratio with an acid and aging. Thus, the size of cationic polynuclear species was controlled which enter in the interlayer spacing resulting in an increase in basal spacing. Expanded layered structure collapsed to its original basal spacing when pillared clay is calcined to 500° (Fig. 1B).

As with basal spacing, surface area also increases (Table 1) from 105 to 204 m² g⁻¹. It is seen from Table 1 that pillared clay retained high surface area (140 m² g⁻¹) even after calcination to 500°. Acid sites of high strength are also observed in iron-pillared clay. Pyridine retention data collected for H-clay and pillared clay are shown

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of (A) iron pillared clay and (B) calcined (500°) sample.

TABLE 1—SURFACE AREA AND BASAL SPACING OF IRON PILLARED CLAY

Sample	Surface area ($\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$)		Basal spacing (Å)	
	300°	500°	300°	500°
H-Clay	105	96	9.70	9.60
Iron pillared clay	204	140	14.70	9.77

in Table 2. It is seen that iron pillared clay has higher pyridine retention capacity than its precursor H-clay. It retained ca. 5% pyridine even after heating to 400° whereas H-clay retained only 2.64%. The number of acid sites evaluated from retention of pyridine at 400° is larger ($4.0 \mu\text{mol pyridine}/\text{m}^2$) than the number of sites measured on conventional alumina pillared clay ($1.6-2.8 \mu\text{mol ammonia}/\text{m}^2$) and the number ($3 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$) reported for the zeolite¹⁵.

TABLE 2—PYRIDINE RETENTION DATA FOR H-CLAY AND IRON PILLARED CLAY

Sample	Retention of pyridine : %/(molecule nm^{-2}) After evacuation at 0.1 mm Hg	After heating for 2 h at				
		110° 200° 300° 400° 500°				
		110°	200°	300°	400°	500°
H-Clay	16.18 (12.83)	12.24 (9.70)	4.18 (3.31)	3.40 (2.70)	2.64 (2.06)	—
Iron-pillared clay	18.42 (10.01)	16.30 (8.86)	8.86 (4.81)	5.48 (2.98)	4.99 (2.71)	0.30 (0.16)

Large surface area and acid sites of high strength of iron pillared clay seem to render the latter a promising catalyst for acid catalysed reactions.

Experimental

A clay sample (supplied by M/s. Jagshanti Mineral Grinding Works, Jodhpur) was used after removing the non-clay materials by conventional sedimentation of aqueous clay slurry. The upgraded clay sample contained (LOI base) SiO_2 , 60.0; R_2O_3 , 32.3; Al_2O_3 , 21.9 and Fe_2O_3 , 10.4; CaO , 3.69; MgO , 1.88 and Na_2O , 1.25%. Cation-exchange capacity of the clay was 86 meq/100 g. Prior to pillaring, it was converted into H-form by passing the clay slurry through the bed of strong base cationic resin (Indion-225) in the hydrogen form.

All the reagents (NH_4Cl , NH_4OH , FeCl_3 , pyridine and HCl) were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of pillaring agent : From the stock solution of Fe^{III} (0.2805 mM Fe/ml), 100 ml was used for the precipitation of Fe^{III} as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ by ($\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} + \text{NH}_4\text{OH}$) solutions. Precipitates were made free from chloride by washing with distilled water and were dissolved in known quantity of standard HCl to get clear solution of OH/Fe ratio of 2.0. It was aged for 108 h at room temperature.

Pillaring process : Known volume of the above pillaring solution was directly added to a known volume of clay slurry containing clay (5 g). It was allowed to interact at room temperature overnight while shaking the mixture and was filtered, washed till free from chloride and dried at 100°.

Analysis : Oriented slides prepared by evaporating a few drops of clay suspension on glass slides were used for XRD analysis. A Philips PW 1820 diffractometer was used with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (Ni-filter).

Adsorption of nitrogen at -196° was used for the measurement of BET surface area (single point). Prior to measurement of surface area, samples were degassed at 250° for 2 h under continuous flow of nitrogen. Relative pressure of 0.3 (p/p_0) of nitrogen was used for single point surface area measurement. For thermal stability study, the 500° (2 h) calcined sample was used for surface area measurement.

To collect the pyridine retention data, calcined sample (500° , 2 h) was equilibrated overnight in a vacuum desiccator over liquid pyridine and evacuated at 0.1 mm of Hg for 2 h at room temperature. After measuring the amount of pyridine sorbed, it was further heated to different temperatures for 2 h and retention of pyridine was measured gravimetrically for each temperature.

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